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Angela Josupeit; Volker Hohmann

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Modeling speech localization, talker identification, and word recognition in a multi-talker setting

Angela Josupeit and Volker Hohmann^{a)}

Medizinische Physik and Cluster of Excellence Hearing4all, Universität Oldenburg, 26111 Oldenburg, Germany

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This study introduces a model for solving three different auditory tasks in a multi-talker setting: target localization, target identification, and word recognition. The model was used to simulate psychoacoustic data from a call-sign-based listening test involving multiple spatially separated talkers [Brungart and Simpson (2007). *Percept. Psychophys.* **69**(1), 79–91]. The main characteristics of the model are (i) the extraction of salient auditory features (“glimpses”) from the multi-talker signal and (ii) the use of a classification method that finds the best target hypothesis by comparing feature templates from clean target signals to the glimpses derived from the multi-talker mixture. The four features used were periodicity, periodic energy, and periodicity-based interaural time and level differences. The model results widely exceeded probability of chance for all subtasks and conditions, and generally coincided strongly with the subject data. This indicates that, despite their sparsity, glimpses provide sufficient information about a complex auditory scene. This also suggests that complex source superposition models may not be needed for auditory scene analysis. Instead, simple models of clean speech may be sufficient to decode even complex multi-talker scenes.

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[VB]

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I. INTRODUCTION

Human listeners are able to understand a given talker in the presence of other talkers, a phenomenon termed the “cocktail party effect” (Cherry, 1953). This task is difficult because the sound signal arriving at the ears is composed of a superposition of signals produced by different sources. Therefore, the auditory system needs to decompose this signal into meaningful streams. This study proposes an auditory model to investigate possible mechanisms involved in the decomposition of a complex input signal originating from a multi-talker scene.

The intelligibility of a target talker among other competing talkers is influenced by a number of factors. Generally speaking, if the auditory features elicited by the different talkers differ from each other, speech intelligibility increases. One of these auditory features is the voice pitch which is related to the fundamental frequency (F0). Darwin *et al.* (2003), for example, showed that speech recognition performance started to increase as the difference in F0, synthetically applied to one of two identical talkers, exceeded two semitones. The reasons for better speech recognition performance with differences in F0, in particular, if two vowel-like signals are presented simultaneously, are summarized by Darwin (2008). The first reason is a low frequency beat that occurs when the two F0s do not differ by more than one semitone (Cullin and Darwin, 1994). Second, the first formants of vowel signals can be apparent when the F0s are

different, but might be invisible when the two F0s are equal. Third, across-formant grouping of concurrently presented formant combinations is impaired if the F0 of the formant combinations is the same (see also Summers *et al.*, 2010). F0 is not only a strong cue for simultaneous masking, but also for sequential streaming (e.g., Moore and Gockel, 2012). Other important auditory features that influence speech intelligibility in multi-talker conditions are binaural features: interaural time difference (ITD) and interaural level difference (ILD). Darwin and Hukin (1999) showed that speech recognition scores were significantly above chance level when ITD differences were 90 μ s or greater, even when there were no differences in the fundamental frequency. Drennan *et al.* (2003) tested the segregation of vowel-like stimuli; they found that ILD differences could significantly enhance performance, even when other cues, in particular, pitch and ITD, were eliminated. Another important grouping cue is spectral shape. Moore and Gockel (2012) argued that if different sounds elicit different excitation patterns, these sounds are easier to segregate. Assmann and Summerfield (1989) found that identification of at least one of two simultaneous synthesized vowels was possible even if the pitch was kept constant and the glottal pulses were temporally aligned. All of the aforementioned studies showed that differences in the speech-relevant features between competing sounds can enhance speech recognition even if the remaining features are similar. In natural listening situations, however, it can be assumed that several features vary at the same time. For example, ITDs and ILDs usually occur in combination. In fact, several studies have shown that the combination of

^{a)}Electronic mail: volker.hohmann@uni-oldenburg.de

several features leads to better speech recognition performance than using any of the features in isolation. In particular, this was observed when ITDs and ILDs were combined (Culling *et al.*, 2004; Drennan *et al.*, 2003), and when spatial cues and fundamental frequency were combined (Du *et al.*, 2011).

For the decoding of complex auditory scenes it may be useful to use only “robust” information, i.e., information that originates from one single source, while ignoring non-robust information originating from source superpositions or reverberation. Faller and Merimaa (2004) used the sub-band interaural coherence to determine which interaural feature values were robust. They successfully predicted sound source location from values of the interaural features that stem from time-frequency bins with an interaural coherence above 0.98. Dietz *et al.* (2011) used a similar measure, the interaural vector strength, to differentiate between robust and non-robust interaural features. The interaural vector strength is a measure for the stability of binaural features within a specific time frame. As a result, location estimates were much more accurate than when all interaural features were used. Josupeit *et al.* (2016) used the same measure to pre-select the robust binaural information before proceeding with further processing steps. This approach was shown to be successful for estimating the location of a single talker in a complex multi-talker environment. In the present study, these robust features are referred to as “glimpses” (Darwin, 2008). The glimpse selection process is purely signal-driven: glimpses provide robust information on a single source, but do not provide any information about whether the source is the target or the masker. In order to decompose the scene into something meaningful, the target-or-masker classification of each glimpse is carried out in subsequent processing steps.

The importance of selecting target glimpses was shown in several studies involving complex scenes with multiple talkers.¹ Usually, target-dominated time-frequency bins are selected using a local signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) threshold, which means that ideal information about the target and masker energy is needed. Best *et al.* (2016) argued that accessing and using target glimpses might be crucial for hearing impaired listeners to understand a target in spatial listening tasks with competing talkers. Schoenmaker and van de Par (2016) manipulated stimuli in a spatial listening task with multiple talkers in such a way that all time-frequency bins of the target stimuli that were below a certain local SNR threshold were discarded from the mixture. They found that speech intelligibility was equally high until the SNR criterion exceeded a value of about 0 dB, indicating that target information below that threshold does not affect speech intelligibility at all. Cooke (2006) was able to successfully predict consonant recognition using an automatic speech recognition system whose only input was the glimpses of target speech. Another auditory model was able to predict localization of a target talker within a multitalker environment using only target-related glimpses (Josupeit *et al.*, 2016). These studies suggest that sparse spectro-temporal target-related information provides sufficient information to solve certain tasks in a complex multi-talker scene. Hence, a complex

model that takes into account all possible changes of target-related information due to a superposition with maskers might not be needed to decode the target-related information. However, for the identification of target-related time-frequency bins, the aforementioned studies used ideal information about the individual target and masker energies. Normally, human listeners are not provided with this information, and therefore methods need to be established that can identify the target-related bins without this idealized information. Josupeit *et al.* (2016) (experiment C), for example, applied a template-based method to identify those bins.

This study introduces an auditory model that uses spectro-temporal glimpses of features to solve localization, identification and word recognition tasks in a multi-talker scenario. The underlying features are (1) periodicity, a feature that is related to the pitch of a sound, (2) periodic energy, which is related to the spectral shape of the periodic sound, and periodicity-based (3) ITD and (4) ILD, which are both related to the azimuthal sound source location. Glimpses are defined as spectro-temporal bins in which the degree of periodicity is high; thus, only periodic content, i.e., voiced speech parts, contribute to the glimpses. It should be emphasized that all features used in this study are periodicity-based, including the energy and binaural features, which was not the case in the earlier study by Josupeit *et al.* (2016) that used coherence-weighting for selecting binaural glimpses. The reason for making all features periodicity-based lies in the importance of periodicity for auditory scene analysis (Darwin, 2008). For deciding whether a glimpse belongs to the talker of interest or not, the model uses a template-matching procedure (e.g., Assmann and Summerfield, 1989). It is assumed that the glimpses from the multi-talker scene resemble the features from the unmasked speech signals; therefore, clean speech was used to generate the templates. The model evaluation was based on a psychoacoustic study by Brungart and Simpson (2007), who measured word recognition in a call-sign-based listening task within a spatial multi-talker setting. The task was to recognize the color and number words of the talker who uttered a specific word, referred to as the “call-sign.” The use of multiple simultaneous speech signals from male talkers creates a highly complex acoustic condition. This challenges the auditory model and enables a critical test of the assumptions underlying our glimpsing approach. The linguistic complexity of the listeners’ task, however, was relatively low. The word limitation enables the use of a detector based on single word templates. These word templates are calculated from the auditory features extracted from different utterances of a word. For this calculation, the same speech corpus as in the experimental procedure is used. The waveforms and hence the extracted features differ slightly for different utterances of the same word, so that the word templates are formed of a distribution of these features.

The aim of this study was to investigate the proposed model in terms of its ability to localize and identify the target talker, and to recognize the color and number words this talker uttered. The word recognition ability was directly compared to the subject performance measured by Brungart and Simpson (2007). A particular research question was

whether a speech model of the unmasked target in combination with robust information taken only from periodic signal segments is sufficient to explain human word recognition performance in multi-talker conditions. In addition, the relative influence of the different experimental parameters and several signal-related measures on model scores was analyzed statistically.

II. METHODS

A. Psychoacoustic study design and data

The model in this study was evaluated with reference to psychoacoustic data collected in a study by [Brungart and Simpson \(2007\)](#). They investigated speech intelligibility in a multi-talker scenario using a call-sign-based listening task. All talkers in a trial simultaneously uttered sentences from the coordinate response measure (CRM) corpus ([Bolia et al., 2000](#)). This corpus consists of sentences of the form, “Ready call sign go to color number now.” Possible call signs are “Arrow,” “Baron,” “Charlie,” “Eagle,” “Hopper,” “Laker,” “Ringo,” and “Tiger.” Color words are “blue,” “red,” “white,” and “green.” Number words are the digits 1 to 8. Thus, one example sentence would be, “Ready Baron go to blue five now.” Recordings from four different male talkers were used.

The concurrent sentences were presented in five different spatial configurations: Two talkers at azimuth locations $\pm 5^\circ$, two talkers at $\pm 90^\circ$, three talkers at 0° and $\pm 15^\circ$, three talkers at 0° and $\pm 90^\circ$, and four talkers at $\pm 90^\circ$ and $\pm 30^\circ$. The target sentence contained the call sign Baron. The masker sentences all had different call signs, color and number words, and were spoken by different talkers. The task of the subject was to recognize the color and number words uttered in the target sentence.

Stimuli were generated using head-related impulse responses (HRIRs) to resemble an anechoic condition. They were presented to the subjects via headphones.

[Brungart and Simpson \(2007\)](#) reported the following findings regarding the influence of the different spatial configurations on word recognition.

- Performance decreased with an increasing number of competing talkers.
- Performance increased with increasing distance between talkers.
- Performance was better when the target sentence was presented at lateral positions rather than at central positions.
- Performance was better when the target was presented in the right rather than in the left hemifield.

It should be noted here that [Brungart and Simpson \(2007\)](#) focused not only on the influence of spatial configuration on word recognition, but also on transition probabilities and transition types. To this end, the target sentence could change in various ways—and with varying probability—from one trial to the next: The target sentence could be spoken by a different talker while all talkers remained fixed at their locations; the target sentence could move from one location to another while being spoken by the same talker; or, the target (and maskers) could randomly change both position and talker identity. In the present modeling study,

however, these transitions and dynamics are not considered. Instead, each sentence presentation was modelled independently of the previous presentations. Therefore, the psychoacoustic reference data used in this study were generated by accumulating the subject data across all of these transition types and transition probabilities.

B. Simulations

1. Stimuli

Sounds were generated using virtual acoustics to simulate an anechoic spatial multi-talker configuration. First, the signals of the individual talkers were generated by setting the whole sentence signal to an root-mean-square of 1 and then convolving it with an HRIR corresponding to the desired azimuth ([Kayser et al., 2009](#)). These HRIRs were recorded in an anechoic room using in-ear microphones in a human head and torso simulator located 80 cm from the sound source in the horizontal plane. Prior to convolution, they were resampled from 48 kHz to $f_s = 40$ kHz, which is the sampling rate of the signals in the speech corpus. HRIRs were recorded at locations from -90° to 0° , and left and right channels were flipped for the respective positive azimuths. Finally, the multi-talker signal was generated by summing up the single talker signals.

The sentences in the speech corpus are synchronized in their onsets (“Ready”). In accordance with the study by [Brungart and Simpson \(2007\)](#), no attempt was made to synchronize the onset of the call sign, color, or number words.

2. Simulation procedure

In line with the psychoacoustic study by [Brungart and Simpson \(2007\)](#), five different spatial configurations were investigated, but different azimuths were used: Two talkers located at $\pm 5^\circ$ azimuth (“two-talker-close”), two talkers at $\pm 60^\circ$ (“two-talker-far”), three talkers at 0° and $\pm 15^\circ$ (“three-talker-close”), three talkers at 0° and $\pm 60^\circ$ (“three-talker-far”), and four talkers at $\pm 20^\circ$ and $\pm 60^\circ$ (“four-talker”). It should be noted here that the talkers in the two-talker-far, three-talker-far, and four-talker conditions were closer together than in the psychoacoustic study. There are two reasons for choosing not to use simulations with talkers located at or near $\pm 90^\circ$: First, the HRTFs we use here are different from those of the subjects. This might lead to problems, specifically at angles of $\pm 90^\circ$, because the interferences at the contralateral ear give rise to large ripples in the HRTF, which are highly individual (“acoustic bright spot,” see [Brungart and Rabinowitz, 1999](#)). Second, the interaural parameters for $\pm 90^\circ$ are the extreme cases of possible interaural parameters. That is, in the template matching procedure, the absolute azimuth location could be systematically underestimated.

As per the psychoacoustical experiment, the target sentence was identified by the call-sign Baron and could be spoken by two, three, or four different, randomly selected talkers from a random location and with random color and number words. The masker sentences were chosen randomly

from the remaining talkers, locations and color and number words.

For the simulations, 100 model runs per spatial condition were executed in order to estimate the variation in performance due to random variation in the signals.

C. Model

The task of the subject was to recognize the color and number words spoken by the talker who uttered the call sign Baron (Brungart and Simpson, 2007). To do this, the subject had to recognize the talker identity and/or location, and remember or track the identity and/or location over time in order to recognize the corresponding color and number words. The model presented in this study therefore performs two steps:

- (1) target localization and identification,
- (2) target color and number word recognition.

Each of these steps was modelled using a basic model structure that was inspired by the “black box of vision” by Gregory (1997). His model describes visual object perception as an interaction of bottom-up, top-down, and selective processes. Bottom-up processes are defined as the signal paths of the sensory organs; top-down processes use perceptual and conceptual knowledge acquired primarily in the past. The specific task can activate processes that select the specific knowledge needed to solve the task. These three processes generate hypotheses about the auditory object before a perceptual decision is made.

Hypothesis-based methods have been widely discussed in the auditory domain as well (e.g., Ellis, 1999), and the present model adopted Gregory’s visual model framework. The bottom-up part of the model is composed of the extraction of auditory features and the selection of robust information (“glimpses”) from the multi-talker input signal. The features used here are periodicity, periodic energy and periodicity-based interaural time and level differences. All features are present as functions of time, auditory frequency channel, and input ear. Glimpsing, i.e., the selection of robust information, is guided by an estimate of the degree of periodicity: Only those features are used for which the energy estimated to stem from a periodic signal exceeds a certain percentage of the overall energy. We assume that one glimpse originates from exactly one source, rather than from a superposition of sources or distorted sources. All feature values for which the energy criterion does not apply are discarded from further processing. More details on feature extraction and glimpsing are given in Sec. IIC 1.

From the specific task and *a priori* knowledge about, for example, the scene setup, hypotheses about the state of the target emerge. For example, if the task was to recognize the color word spoken by the target talker, relevant *a priori* knowledge would include knowledge about the limited set of color words (blue, red, white, and green) as well as the target identity and its location. This leads to the hypothesis that the target word is either blue, red, white, or green, spoken by the identified talker at the identified location. Section IIC 2 a

provides more details about hypothesis generation for different kinds of tasks and *a priori* knowledge.

The present model simulates top-down processes as the implementation of perceptual knowledge in the form of templates. Template matching is a relatively simple method that utilizes existing knowledge for classification in an optimal form. The templates used here are generated from the glimpses extracted from clean word utterances (details are described in Sec. IIC 2 b). The selection of templates is based on the previously generated hypotheses. For the aforementioned example, only the templates of the words blue, red, white, and green, spoken by the identified talker at the identified location, are used.

Each of the selected templates is then compared to the glimpses of the bottom-up process. Here, this process is referred to as “template matching.” The better a template matches the glimpses, the greater the support for the corresponding hypothesis. The details of the template-matching method are described in Sec. IIC 2 c.

The final perceptual decision is essentially based on the best hypothesis, i.e., the hypothesis with the highest support. More details of the decision process are described in Sec. IIC 2 d.

1. Feature extraction and glimpsing

Four auditory features are extracted separately for a number of frequency bands from the multi-talker input signal: periodicity P , periodic energy E , and periodicity-based interaural time and level differences, T and L . The features were extracted from pre-selected signal segments that covered the target words, i.e., either the call-sign Baron, or the color or number word uttered by this talker. This implies that the model uses *a priori* knowledge about the time position of the target words within the multi-talker mixture, and about the word duration.

Figure 1 illustrates the extraction of periodicity features and glimpsing. This process is divided into five steps, which are indicated by the numbers in the left of the figure. Each of these steps is detailed in the following.

- (1) First, the left and right input signals pass an auditory pre-processing stage based on the preprocessing used by Dietz *et al.* (2011).
 - (a) Middle ear bandpass filter consisting of a second-order Butterworth filter with 500 Hz lower and 2000 Hz cutoff frequency.
 - (b) An auditory filterbank consisting of fourth-order gammatone filters with center frequencies ranging from approximately $f_c = 200$ Hz to $f_c = 5000$ Hz; one filter per ERB (equivalent rectangular bandwidth) is implemented, resulting in a total of 23 frequency channels.
 - (c) Hair-cell processing consisting of a half-wave rectification and a compression with the power of 0.4. A fifth-order low-pass filter with 770 Hz cutoff frequency was implemented for all signals originating from filters with $f_c > 1400$ Hz.
 - (d) Differentiation stage to remove the DC component of the hair-cell signals; this procedure allows a

FIG. 1. Illustration of periodicity feature extraction and glimpsing. See text for details.

more precise calculation of periodicity features. This stage was not originally implemented by Dietz *et al.* (2011),

- (e) Fine structure filter for all frequency bands with a center frequency of $f_c < 1400$ Hz, and envelope filter for all frequency bands with $f_c > 1400$ Hz. Fine structure filters and envelope filters were second-order gammatone filters. The center frequency of the fine structure filters was set to f_c , and the

bandwidth to $f_c/3$. The center frequency of all envelope filters was set to 250 Hz with a bandwidth of 250 Hz, respectively. Therefore, the envelope filter covers the typical range of the human voice pitch.

The resulting signals are time signals, extracted in each frequency band $c \in \{1, 2, \dots, 23\}$, and each input channel $s \in \{1, 2\}$ (left and right).

- (2) The preprocessed signal in each frequency channel is further analysed at consecutive time steps n that have a spacing of 10 ms. Around each considered time step, eight signal segments of length P' are formed, shown as the dashed lines in Fig. 1. P' is varied from $(1400 \text{ Hz})^{-1}$ to $(80 \text{ Hz})^{-1}$ in steps of 0.025 ms. The energy of the signal that spans all eight signal segments (solid black curve at stage 2) is termed *total energy*. It is calculated as the mean square amplitudes of the signal.
- (3) The eight signal segments are averaged which leads to a nominal increase in the signal-to-noise ratio of 9 dB for uncorrelated noise, allowing for a robust periodicity feature extraction. In the following, these averaged signals are referred to as (periodicity) base functions. The energy of the base functions is termed *periodic energy* which corresponds to the mean square amplitudes of the base function.
- (4) One point in the normalized synchrogram shows the *normalized periodic energy* which is defined as the ratio of the periodic energy and the total energy. The whole normalized synchrogram is composed of normalized energy values for different time steps n and different signal segment lengths corresponding to the evaluated period P' . The normalized synchrogram contains values between 0 and 1. Values are close to 1 if the 8 signal segments superimpose constructively so that the periodic energy approaches the total energy. This means that values close to 1 indicate a high harmonic content with the considered period P' . Values of 0 indicate that the considered period P' is not present in the signal.
- (5) Large normalized periodic energy values indicate that the corresponding information is robust, i.e., it likely originates from one talker. In the present modeling study, the focus lies on this robust information. Thus, only those periodicity values are selected that show large normalized periodic energy values in the synchrogram. This process is termed “glimpsing” and is implemented as follows. For each time step n , the normalized periodic energy is regarded as a function of P' (which corresponds to one column in the synchrogram, see top of Fig. 1). All local maxima of this function are extracted (shown as crosses in stage 5 of Fig. 1). A local maximum is defined as a value whose two neighbouring values are lower. For the glimpsing process, two criteria are investigated. First, the harmonic content of the signal must be high enough. It is assumed that this criterion is met when the largest local maximum exceeds a value of 0.9 (for fine structure filtered signals; see dashed line in stage 5 of Fig. 1), i.e., the periodic energy accounts for 90% of the signal energy. For envelope filtered signals, the threshold was set to 0.5 (see also Josupeit *et al.*, 2016).

This corresponds to the periodic energy accounting for 50% of the signal energy, i.e., a SNR of 0 dB at the tested periodicity. This yielded a sufficient number of glimpses at a sufficiently high SNR above 0 dB. With the second criterion, all local maxima are selected that exceeded a value of 0.8 (fine structure filtered signals) or 0.4 (envelope filtered signals). The selected glimpses based on these criteria are illustrated as circles in stage 5 of Fig. 1. Note that it is possible to extract more than one glimpse for one n : This is a consequence of the choice of window lengths P' . It is thus possible to extract not only the fundamental period, but also multiples of this fundamental period. Accordingly, if more than one glimpse is extracted for one particular n , this does not imply that several talkers are active at the same time, but that these glimpses belong to the same talker.

The resulting periodicity features are termed P_{cns} , with the index cns referring to the auditory channel c , time bin n , and side s (left or right). P_{cns} is defined as a set that can consist of either a single or multiple values, or no value at all.

Figure 2 illustrates the extraction of all auditory features including periodicity, periodic energy, and periodicity-based ILDs and ITDs for the left ear ($s = 1$; the extraction of features for the right ear is done analogously). The periodic energy features, referred to as E_{cns} , were set as periodic energies, i.e., the energies of the periodicity base functions, corresponding to the glimpsed periods in the set P_{cns} . The extraction of ILDs and ITDs, referred to as L_{cns} and T_{cns} , is based on the periodicity base functions of the left and right ear processing (see solid and dashed lines in Fig. 2). The left ear base function (solid line) corresponds to a periodicity glimpse extracted from the left ear processing. The right ear base function (dashed line) corresponds to the right ear periodicity base function at the same period. Note that this period does not necessarily correspond to a right-ear-glimpse. Hence, it is possible to get different ILD and ITD values for the left and right side.

ILDs L_{cns} are calculated as the subtraction of logarithmized right and left ear periodic energies of these base functions. ITDs T_{cns} are extracted by calculating the cross-correlation function of the left and right base functions. Essentially, the maximum location of the cross correlation function is then defined as the ITD. Because ambiguities between left and right ITDs are possible, a case differentiation based on the extracted ILDs is applied, so that the extracted ITDs are defined as

- the maximum of the positive section of the cross correlation function if the corresponding ILD exceeds 1 dB, or as
- the maximum of the negative section of the cross correlation function if the corresponding ILD falls below -1 dB, or as
- the overall maximum of the cross correlation function if the corresponding ITD is between -1 dB and 1 dB

2. Classification

a. Defining hypotheses. Step 1 of the model is to localize and identify the target talker, which is the talker who uttered the call sign Baron in the multi-talker mixture. The model's task is therefore to estimate the location $\hat{\alpha}$ and identity \hat{i} of the target talker. The relevant *a priori* knowledge stems from knowledge about the acoustic condition as well as from previous training sessions. It is assumed that the model knows that the range of possible locations is restricted to the frontal field, i.e., from -90° to $+90^\circ$. It is also assumed that the fixed set of talker identities is known, i.e., talkers A and B in the two-talker conditions; A , B , and C in the three-talker conditions; and A , B , C , and D in the four-talker condition. Altogether, the hypotheses for model step 1 are all possible combinations of locations

$$\alpha_{\text{hyp}} = \{-90^\circ, -85^\circ, \dots, 85^\circ, 90^\circ\} \quad (1)$$

and talker identities (three-talker condition as an example).

FIG. 2. Illustration of feature extraction. See text for details.

$$i_{\text{hyp}} = \{A, B, C\}. \quad (2)$$

Thus, there were 74 different hypotheses tested for the two-talker conditions ($37 \text{ locations} \times 2 \text{ identities}$), 111 hypotheses for the three-talker conditions (37×3), and 148 hypotheses for the four-talker condition (37×4). Note that all hypotheses are related to the target state. Thus, no additional hypotheses about the call-sign are defined, because only one call-sign, Baron, is defined as the target.

Step 2 of the model is to estimate the color/number words the target uttered, referred to as $\hat{c}\hat{o}/\hat{n}\hat{u}$. Here, it is assumed that the set of possible color/number words is known. Furthermore, from model step 1, the target location $\hat{\alpha}$ and identity \hat{i} are also available. Therefore, the hypotheses for the color word can be written as

$$\text{co}_{\text{hyp}} = \{\text{blue}_{\hat{\alpha}, \hat{i}}, \text{red}_{\hat{\alpha}, \hat{i}}, \text{white}_{\hat{\alpha}, \hat{i}}, \text{green}_{\hat{\alpha}, \hat{i}}\}, \quad (3)$$

and the hypotheses for the number word as

$$\text{nu}_{\text{hyp}} = \{\text{one}_{\hat{\alpha}, \hat{i}}, \text{two}_{\hat{\alpha}, \hat{i}}, \dots, \text{eight}_{\hat{\alpha}, \hat{i}}\}. \quad (4)$$

The subindices $(\cdot)_{\hat{\alpha}, \hat{i}}$ indicate that the corresponding word is spoken by the talker with the identity \hat{i} from the location $\hat{\alpha}$. Note there are four hypotheses for color word recognition and eight for number word recognition.

b. Template generation. Each hypothesis is represented by a template calculated based on the extracted auditory features from clean word signals. The template generation process is illustrated in Fig. 3. For each word w , each talker identity i , and each possible location α , this process involves the following steps.

- (1) Single-word stimuli are generated as described in Sec. II B 1, but without the maskers. The speech corpus contains a number of possible utterances for a word w , spoken by a talker i , which slightly differ from each other. For the call-sign (Baron) and each of the number words, there are 32 utterances per talker; for each of the color words, there are 64 utterances per talker.
- (2) The auditory features are extracted as described in Sec. II C 1 from all possible utterances of an unmasked word. The black circles in the left panel of Fig. 3 show the

extracted periodicity features from the clean word Baron, spoken by the talker $i=A$ at $\alpha = 60^\circ$, for one *cn*s bin. Each column corresponds to the extracted features for a possible utterance of the word Baron.

- (3) Gaussian kernels are assigned to each extracted feature value, indicated as the black solid curves in the left panel of Fig. 3. Gaussian kernels are defined as normal distributions whose expected value corresponds to the current feature value and whose standard deviation, i.e., the width of the kernel, is defined by the parameter σ . The value for σ depends on the auditory feature type.
 - The energy JND is relatively constant, approximately 1 dB, across different frequencies (Zwicker and Fastl, 2007), thus,

$$\sigma_E = 1 \text{ dB}. \quad (5)$$

- The ITD JND depends on both the stimulus frequency and the reference ITD. According to interaural phase difference (IPD) JND data from Yost (1974), for example, a 500 Hz tone with a reference IPD of 0° has an IPD JND of 3° , corresponding to approximately $17 \mu\text{s}$. The IPD JND for the same tone with a reference IPD of 135° is 15° , corresponding to approximately $83^\circ \mu\text{s}$. The Gaussian kernel width was set to a value at the lower edge of the range

$$\sigma_T = 25 \mu\text{s}, \quad (6)$$

so that it is suitable for all possible target locations.

- The ILD JND fluctuates relatively little, from approximately 0.7 to 1.5 dB across different frequencies between 200 and 5000 Hz and reference ILDs of up to 9 dB (Yost and Dye, 1988). Therefore, we assumed a constant value of

$$\sigma_L = 1 \text{ dB}. \quad (7)$$

- The frequency JND is approximately 1 Hz for frequencies up to 500 Hz and approximately $0.002f$ for frequencies above 500 Hz (Zwicker and Fastl, 2007). The corresponding JNDs in terms of periodicity, however, are much smaller than the differences in periodicity values extracted from different utterances of the same

FIG. 3. Illustration of template generation (periodicity features) for one *cn*s bin (left), and the resulting template as a function of n (right). The auditory features (black circles) are extracted from all possible utterances of unmasked representations of a word (here: Baron). The template is generated by summing up Gaussian kernels with an expected value equal to the feature values and a standard deviation of σ . The normalization constant C is chosen so that the integral of the resulting function is equal to 1.

word by the same talker. Therefore, we decided to base the Gaussian kernel width on these across-utterance differences rather than on the frequency JND. This makes sure that the Gaussian kernels are wide enough to allow for a clear representation of the maxima in the template. If the width would be too small, the template in Fig. 3, for example, would not have four major maxima, but rather many minor maxima, distributed along the major maxima. The kernel width was therefore set to

$$\sigma_P = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{20f_c(c)} & \text{if } f_c(c) < 1.4 \text{ kHz,} \\ \frac{1}{20 \times 250 \text{ Hz}} = 0.2 \text{ ms} & \text{if } f_c(c) > 1.4 \text{ kHz.} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Note that the channels with $f_c(c) > 1.4$ kHz are modulation channels with a center modulation frequency of 250 Hz.

- (4) The sum of the Gaussian kernels across all extracted features from all utterances forms the template for one *cms*-bin. The sum is normalized using a normalization constant C to make the integral of the resulting function equal to one. That is, the templates are formed of probability density functions (PDFs). This leads to one column of the template (right panel of Fig. 3).

c. Support for each hypothesis using template matching. Given the glimpses extracted from the multi-talker signal, the next aim is to calculate the support these

glimpses provide for each hypothesis as defined in Eqs. (1)–(4). The first step for calculating the support is to calculate the probabilities that the observed features P_{cms} , E_{cms} , L_{cms} , and T_{cms} origin from a talker i , a location α and a word w , as defined by the current template (see Fig. 4). These probabilities are calculated as follows.

- (1) For each feature value in the set P_{cms} , E_{cms} , L_{cms} , and T_{cms} , the integral about this value is calculated numerically using the trapezoid rule applied to the left and right neighbouring values.² The difference between neighbouring values refers to the evaluation points on the PDF. It was set to $\Delta\hat{P} = 0.05$ ms, $\Delta\hat{E} = 1$ dB, $\Delta\hat{T} = 25$ μ s, and $\Delta\hat{L} = 1$ dB.
- (2) For P_{cms} , the sum of the integral values across the entries of P_{cms} is calculated. For E_{cms} , L_{cms} , and T_{cms} , the mean instead of the sum is calculated, because the templates of these features have one peak instead of multiple peaks as seen for the periodicity features (see Fig. 4).
- (3) Due to the limited accuracy of the numerical integration, it is possible for probability values to exceed a value of 1; all values greater than 1 are set to 1. If the feature set is empty, i.e., no glimpse was extracted, the probability is set to zero. Example probability functions are shown in Fig. 4 in the panels below the template plots. The probabilities are termed $p(P_{cms}|w, i, \alpha)$, $p(E_{cms}|w, i, \alpha)$, $p(T_{cms}|w, i, \alpha)$, and $p(L_{cms}|w, i, \alpha)$.

The second step for calculating the support is the multiplication of the probabilities across features, assuming that the individual feature probabilities are statistically independent,

FIG. 4. Sample templates, multi-talker features, and resulting support functions. Each of the four panels represents one auditory feature. The shaded 2D plots show the templates for the word $w = \text{Baron}$, spoken by the talker with identity $i = A$ from $\alpha = 60^\circ$. Templates, features, and support functions are shown as a function of time index n for frequency channel $c = 3$, corresponding to $f_c = 348.4$ Hz, and the left ear ($s = 1$). The black circles show sample features that were extracted from a multi-talker signal with three talkers located at 0° and $\pm 60^\circ$. Each of them uttered a call-sign word; the talker at $+60^\circ$ matched the plotted template, i.e., identity $i = A$ and $w = \text{Baron}$. The panels below the template and feature plots show the support functions that result from the template matching procedure.

$$p_{cns}(w, i, \alpha) = \frac{K_{cns}(w, i, \alpha)}{K_w} \prod_{o \in \{P, E, L, T\}} p(o_{cns} | w, i, \alpha). \quad (9)$$

The first factor corresponds to the probability of glimpsing. It is defined as the number of glimpses found in the different utterances of the word for this particular frequency channel c , time frame n , and side s , K_{cns} , divided by the total number of utterances K_w . K_w is a maximum limit for K_{cns} , so that the quotient assumes values between 0 and 1. The calculation of a product ensures that high support only occurs when there is a good template match for all features. Note that if no glimpse is observed in a cns -bin, the support is zero. The support for a whole observation ranging across all frequency channels c , times n , and sides s is calculated as the mean value of the individual probabilities,

$$p_{1:C,1:N,1:2}(w, i, \alpha) = \frac{1}{2CN} \sum_c \sum_n \sum_s p_{cns}(w, i, \alpha). \quad (10)$$

C is the number of channels, N is the number of time samples of the features extracted from the multi-talker signal. Therefore, N is equal to the target word duration, because the features were extracted from the signal segments that covered the target word. An example for the mean probability is shown in Fig. 5 for $w = \text{Baron}$, $i \in i_{\text{hyp}}$, and $\alpha \in \alpha_{\text{hyp}}$ (top left panel).

To get information about the locations of *all* talkers, referred to as “scene location statistics,” only the location-related features (L and T) are considered:

$$p_{\alpha;cns}(w, i, \alpha) = \frac{K_{cns}(w, i, \alpha)}{K_w} \prod_{o \in \{L, T\}} p(o_{cns} | w, i, \alpha) \quad (11)$$

and

$$p_{\alpha;1:C,1:N,1:2}(w, i, \alpha) = \frac{1}{2CN} \sum_c \sum_n \sum_s p_{\alpha;cns}(w, i, \alpha). \quad (12)$$

An example for this function (for $w = \text{Baron}$ and summed across different i) is illustrated in Fig. 5 (right panel, dashed line).

d. Decision. Model step 1 estimates the location and identity of the target. The keyword that guides this process is the word *Baron*. Therefore, the index w could be regarded as one constant value and is omitted in the following. For the estimation of the target location, all probabilities regarding α are accumulated. Consequently, the location statistics for the target are defined as

$$p_{1:C,1:N,1:2}(\alpha) = C_{0,1} \cdot \sum_{i \in i_{\text{hyp}}} p_{1:C,1:N,1:2}(i, \alpha \in \alpha_{\text{hyp}}). \quad (13)$$

FIG. 5. Illustration of the decision process of model step 1 (localization and identification). The top left panel shows the support for each location hypothesis α_{hyp} and identity hypothesis i_{hyp} . The right panel shows the location statistics. The solid black curve was calculated by summing up and normalizing the support shown in the left panel across talker identities. The dashed black curve was calculated from the support provided by all location-related features (not shown). The location estimate was the maximum position of the difference function. The target identity estimate was the maximum position of the original support matrix (top left panel) at the estimated target location, illustrated by the white dashed lines.

An example for this function is shown in Fig. 5 (right panel, solid black line). Using Eq. (12), the location statistics for the whole scene are defined as

$$p_{\alpha;1:C,1:N,1:2}(\alpha) = C_{0,2} \cdot \sum_{i \in h_{\text{hyp}}} p_{\alpha;1:C,1:N,1:2}(i, \alpha \in \alpha_{\text{hyp}}) \quad (14)$$

(see Fig. 5, dashed line). $C_{0,1}$ and $C_{0,2}$ are normalization constants to obtain an overall sum of 1. The scene location statistics are used to “refine” the target location statistics. Such a mechanism was previously applied in a localization model by Josupeit *et al.* (2016) for localizing a target talker in a multi-talker scene with the aim to improve target detection by analyzing target-related information conditioned on the actual distribution of sources (target and maskers) in the scene. For this, the target location estimation is based on the difference function of the two statistics,

$$\hat{\alpha} = \underset{\alpha}{\operatorname{argmax}}(p_{1:C,1:N,1:2}(\alpha) - p_{\alpha;1:C,1:N,1:2}(\alpha)). \quad (15)$$

An illustration of this process is also shown in Fig. 5 (right panel, gray curve and asterisk). This procedure leads to an emphasis of the target talker location; the masker locations are suppressed. The target talker identification is based on the previously estimated target location,

$$\hat{i} = \underset{i}{\operatorname{argmax}}(p_{1:C,1:N,1:2}(i, \alpha = \hat{\alpha})), \quad (16)$$

see Fig. 5 (bottom left panel).

Model step 2 aims to recognize the target color/number words. This decision is based on the estimated target location $\hat{\alpha}$ and identity \hat{i} [see also Eqs. (3) and (4)]. The color and number word probabilities are computed using Eq. (10) as

$$p_{1:C,1:N_{\text{co}},1:2}(\text{co}) = p_{1:C,1:N_{\text{co}},1:2}(w = \text{co}, i = \hat{i}, \alpha = \hat{\alpha}) \quad (17)$$

and

$$p_{1:C,1:N_{\text{nu}},1:2}(\text{nu}) = p_{1:C,1:N_{\text{nu}},1:2}(w = \text{nu}, i = \hat{i}, \alpha = \hat{\alpha}), \quad (18)$$

calculated for all $\text{co} \in \text{co}_{\text{hyp}}$ and $\text{nu} \in \text{nu}_{\text{hyp}}$. N_{co} and N_{nu} define the target color/number word duration in samples within the multi-talker scene. The estimated color and number words are those words with the highest support,

$$\hat{\text{co}} = \underset{\text{co}}{\operatorname{argmax}}(p_{1:C,1:N_{\text{co}},1:2}(\text{co})) \quad (19)$$

and

$$\hat{\text{nu}} = \underset{\text{nu}}{\operatorname{argmax}}(p_{1:C,1:N_{\text{nu}},1:2}(\text{nu})). \quad (20)$$

D. Measures for analyzing model scores

In order to get more insight into the factors influencing model scores, two measures were used: Target speech proportion and feature distortion.

1. Target speech proportion

The target speech proportion (TSP) was defined as

$$\text{TSP} = \frac{\text{number of target-dominated cns-bins}}{\text{number of cns-bins}}. \quad (21)$$

Target-dominated cns-bins are those bins for which the local SNR, SNR_{cns} , is higher than 3 dB (Cooke, 2006). The energy signals underlying the calculation of SNR_{cns} were extracted as in Eq. (A4), using the target and masker signals in isolation as input signals.

2. Feature distortion

Feature distortion (FD) is a measure of how much the glimpses extracted from the multi-talker signal actually deviate from the clean signals. This measure was basically calculated by comparing the multi-talker glimpses, P_{cns} [see Eq. (A9)], at target-dominated bins with the glimpses extracted from the target alone, $P_{\text{tar,cns}}$. The feature difference was then defined as

$$e_{P,\text{cns}} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sigma_P} (P_{1,\text{tar,cns}} - P_{1,\text{cns}}) & \text{if } \text{SNR}_{\text{cns}} > 3 \text{ dB} \wedge P_{\text{tar,cns}} \neq \emptyset \wedge P_{\text{cns}} \neq \emptyset, \\ \text{NaN} & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

The subindex 1 refers to the first element in the feature sets $P_{\text{tar,cns}}$ and P_{cns} , which represent the periodicity values of the clean target and the mixed signal, respectively. The feature differences are expressed in units of σ_P [see Eq. (8)] to provide a measure for the effect of feature distortions on the template-matching procedure. The final feature distortion measure FD_P was then the average of all absolute values ($\neq \text{NaN}$) of $e_{P,\text{cns}}$ across channels c , time instances n and sides s . The feature distortions of

the other features, FD_E , FD_T , and FD_L , were calculated analogously.

III. RESULTS

A. Target localization and identification

Figure 6 shows the model results for localization (top) and identification (bottom) of the target talker in the multi-talker mixture. The results are shown as percent correct

FIG. 6. Model results for localization (top) and identification (bottom) of the target talker in the multi-talker mixture. Gray bars show the model percent correct scores as a function of target location. The results are grouped according to spatial condition. Black horizontal lines indicate the probability of guessing.

scores as a function of target location. A location estimate counted as correct if the estimated target location was closer to the true target location than to any of the masker locations. The probabilities of guessing, shown as the horizontal black lines in Fig. 6, were calculated based on this

assumption. An identity estimate counted as correct if the true target identity was estimated. Given that the number of possible target identities was limited to 2 to 4, the corresponding guessing probabilities ranged from $\frac{1}{2}$ to $\frac{1}{4}$, independent of the target location. A one-tailed binomial test with 5% significance level was performed on each score to test whether the model percent correct scores were significantly higher than the probability of guessing: This was found to be the case for all localization and identification scores.

B. Word recognition

Figure 7 shows the model and subject results for color and number word recognition. Two versions of the model were implemented: First, a model that used the previously estimated target location and identity as described in Sec. II C 2 d, Eqs. (17)–(20) (light gray bars); second, a model that used the true target location and identity (dark gray bars). The second model version therefore provides information about the isolated performance of the word recognition method described here, independent of localization and identification performance.

A recognition estimate counted as correct if the color and number words were both correctly identified in a run. Black horizontal lines show the probability of guessing, which was calculated as $\frac{1}{4} \times \frac{1}{8} = \frac{1}{32}$ for four possible color words and eight possible number words. A one-tailed binomial test, performed for each percent correct score separately, showed that the model scores were significantly higher than chance level; this was true for both the default model as well as the model with ideal prior information about the target location and identity.

A one-tailed binomial test was also applied to find significant differences between the model and the subject results. The asterisks at the top of Fig. 7 identify whether the

FIG. 7. Model and subject results for color and number word recognition. Dark gray bars show the model results for a model version that uses the true target location and identity as prior knowledge. Light gray bars show the model results for the model version that uses the previously estimated target location and identity as prior knowledge. Black circles show the subject results from Brungart and Simpson (2007) (their Fig. 6). Note that for some conditions the target locations in the psychoacoustic setup were different from those used in the model simulations; these conditions are marked by asterisks. Black horizontal lines show the probability of guessing. Dark and light gray stars on top of the figure indicate a significant difference between model and subject percent correct scores.

model scores were significantly different from the subject scores. It should be emphasized here that the spatial spread of talker locations was higher in the psychoacoustic study than in the model simulations. Therefore, the “far” conditions can only provide a rough guide for comparing the model with the subject data.

C. Factors influencing model scores

1. Experimental variables

The influence of the following external variables on model scores was tested.

- Number of talkers $N \in \{2, 3, 4\}$. Brungart and Simpson (2007) found that subject performance decreased significantly with increasing number of competing talkers.
- Target azimuth $\alpha \in \{0^\circ, 5^\circ, 15^\circ, 20^\circ, 60^\circ\}$. Brungart and Simpson (2007) found that subjects perform differently for central vs lateral target positions. Here, we restricted the possible target positions to the absolute values, because we assumed that the model scores would be the same whether the target was placed in the left or in the right hemifield. The psychoacoustic data, however, showed significant improvements in performance for target positions in the right hemifield compared to the left hemifield (Brungart and Simpson, 2007). The model did

not include a stage that takes these left-right differences into account.

- Distance to closest masker $\Delta \in \{10^\circ, 15^\circ, 40^\circ, 60^\circ, 120^\circ\}$. This variable is related to the observation of subject performance differences for close vs far conditions (Brungart and Simpson, 2007). Hawley *et al.* (1999) used the distance to the closest masker as one parameter (in addition to the number of talkers) in a speech recognition task; they found a significant influence of this distance on speech recognition.
- Target identity $ID \in \{A, B, C, D\}$.
- Target word $w \in \{\text{blue, red, white, green}\}$ for color word recognition, or $w \in \{\text{one, two, \dots, eight}\}$ for number word recognition.

The influence of these variables on the responses in the respective tasks was tested with a logistic regression model (LRM) that included interaction terms.³ The influence of each variable on model scores is shown in Table I.

a. Number of talkers. The number of talkers N in the scene only had a direct impact on identification performance. However, the interaction of N with the target azimuth α had a significant influence on identification and localization performance. This can be interpreted such that the influence of target azimuth α on performance is different depending on N ; and vice versa, that the influence of N on performance

TABLE I. Estimated coefficients β and their standard error SE for each variable of the logistic regression model (LRM); significant levels identify whether the coefficients contribute to the model for the null hypothesis that $\beta = 0$, t-statistic. Each column shows one task; the color and number word recognition scores are taken from the ideal model version (with perfect *a priori* knowledge about the target location and identity). Colons describe interaction terms. Variables labeled “deleted” yielded perfect performance and therefore had to be discarded from the model. The last row shows the χ^2 values for the whole LRM; significance levels indicate whether the LRM differed from using a constant model (for the null hypothesis that the models have the same deviance, χ^2 -statistic).

Variable	Identification	Localization	Color word rec.	number word rec.
	Regression coefficients β (SE)			
(Intercept)	12.84(3.44) ^a	7.90(2.28) ^a	-3.42(2.88)	1.07(1.76)
Number of talkers N	-2.33(1.02) ^b	-1.10(0.79)	1.80(1.06)	0.90(0.61)
Dist. to closest masker Δ	-0.07(0.08)	0.05(0.07)	0.23(0.11) ^b	0.03(0.06)
Target azimuth α	-0.37(0.11) ^a	-0.29(0.11) ^c	0.07(0.15)	0.10(0.09)
Target identity ID = B	-2.38(0.49) ^a	-2.06(0.49) ^a	-0.36(0.47)	-0.12(0.39)
Target identity ID = C	0.55(0.68)	-0.07(0.59)	0.26(0.76)	-1.04(0.44) ^b
Target identity ID = D	-1.59(0.68) ^b	-1.38(0.70) ^b	-2.75(0.87) ^c	-1.40(0.65) ^b
Interaction $N:\Delta$	0.003(0.025)	-0.03(0.02)	-0.08(0.04) ^b	-0.02(0.02)
Interaction $N:\alpha$	0.07(0.02) ^a	0.07(0.02) ^c	0.007(0.031)	-0.03(0.02)
Interaction $\Delta:\alpha$	0.003(0.001) ^c	0.0018(0.0008) ^b	-0.002(0.001)	0.00006(0.00071)
Color word $w = \text{red}$			1.08(0.44) ^b	
Color word $w = \text{white}$			deleted	
Color word $w = \text{green}$			2.29(0.70) ^a	
Number word $w = \text{two}$				-1.34(0.72)
Number word $w = \text{three}$				-2.04(0.71) ^c
Number word $w = \text{four}$				-1.16(0.72)
Number word $w = \text{five}$				deleted
Number word $w = \text{six}$				-1.15(0.71)
Number word $w = \text{seven}$				0.56(0.97)
Number word $w = \text{eight}$				0.10(0.82)
	total model statistics (χ^2 vs constant model)			
	120 ^a	96.5 ^a	35.5 ^a	57 ^a

^a $p < 0.001$.

^b $p < 0.05$.

^c $p < 0.01$.

depends on α . Thus, the influence of N on identification and localization performance (Fig. 6) can be illustrated by looking at the data for constant α . For $\alpha = \pm 60^\circ$, performance decreased from almost 100% for $N=2$ to approximately 90% (localization)/84% (identification) for $N=3$ and 91%/87% for $N=4$. For the central target positions ($\alpha \leq 5^\circ$), a similar trend was observed: performance dropped from almost 100% for $N=2$ to approximately 92% (localization)/92% (identification) in the close condition and 72%/69% in the far condition for $N=3$. Furthermore, the performance for medial target positions, i.e., $\alpha = \pm 15^\circ$ and $\alpha = \pm 20^\circ$, decreased from 86%/88% for $N=3$ to 64%/68% for $N=4$.

Interestingly, the number of talkers did not seem to have a large impact on word recognition performance (for the ideal model version). The slightly decreased performance for $N=4$ compared to $N=3$ seen in Fig. 7 may be due in part to the influence of the talker identity $ID = D$, which was only present in the four-talker condition.

b. Target azimuth. The target azimuth α affected both identification and localization performance, both as a main effect and in interactions with N and Δ . For $N=4$, the mean performance for $\alpha = \pm 20^\circ$ was approximately 64% (localization)/68% (identification) and for $\alpha = \pm 60^\circ$ it was approximately 91%/87%. For $N=3$, differences between target azimuths were observed as well, most clearly for the three-talker-far condition: Here, although Δ was constant for all target azimuths, performance dropped from approximately 90% (localization)/84% (identification) for $\alpha = \pm 60^\circ$ to approximately 72%/69% for $\alpha = 0^\circ$. The target azimuth did not seem to play a role for $N=2$, where model scores were almost 100% for all conditions.

Target azimuth had no significant effect on word recognition (ideal model).

c. Distance to closest masker. The closest target-to-masker distance Δ did not have a main effect on model scores for localization, identification and number word recognition, and had only a small significant effect on color word recognition. The interaction of Δ and α was significant for identification and localization. This interaction was most prominent for the three-talker condition: model scores for $\alpha = 0^\circ$ differed significantly depending on the distance to the maskers. Performance decreased from 92% (localization)/92% (identification) for $\Delta = 15^\circ$ to 72%/69% for $\Delta = 60^\circ$. Δ did not seem to play a role for $N=2$ for localization and identification, where model scores was almost 100% for all conditions. For word recognition, however, performance increased from approximately 80% for $\Delta = 10^\circ$ to 94% for $\Delta = 120^\circ$. For $N=4$, the masker distance was the same for all locations ($\Delta = 40^\circ$).

d. Talker identity. The dependence of model scores on target talker identity was difficult to interpret because the only condition in which all four talkers were presented as possible target talkers was the four-talker condition. Each ID-related coefficient in Table I must be read with respect to $ID = A$. That is, the talker identity $ID = B$ had a negative impact on model scores compared to $ID = A$, at least for

identification and localization. The same was true for $ID = D$, for which a slightly negative effect compared to $ID = A$ was observed for all tasks. However, this talker was only present in the four-talker conditions.

e. Color and number words. The coefficients for color word recognition must be read with respect to the word $w = \text{blue}$. Thus, the target words $w = \text{red}$ and $w = \text{green}$ were recognized significantly better than the word $w = \text{blue}$. All runs including the word $w = \text{white}$ had to be deleted from the LRM because this word was recognized in 100% of the runs.

An analogous interpretation for the number words revealed only a significantly lower recognition rate (compared to $w = \text{one}$) for $w = \text{three}$. As with the word white in the color recognition LRM, all runs containing the word $w = \text{five}$ had to be excluded from the LRM because this word was recognized in 100% of the runs.

2. Target speech proportion

The TSP was calculated as described in Sec. IID 1, for each run separately. For identification and localization, the speech section containing the word Baron was used as an input; for color and number word recognition, the speech sections containing the target's color and number words were used. Figure 8 shows the TSP as a function of absolute target azimuth for the five spatial conditions. The TSP was around 31% for the two-talker conditions, and decreased to values of around 17% for three talkers and 13% for four talkers. The variation between TSPs within conditions was rather large. To explore the relation between the TSP and the experimental variables in Table I, partial correlations were calculated for each of the variables (N , Δ , and α) and the TSP for each run, while controlling for the respective other variables, see Table II (first column). The TSP correlated only with the number of talkers; this is also shown in Fig. 8.

FIG. 8. Mean and standard deviations of the target speech proportion as a function of target location for the five spatial conditions.

TABLE II. Partial correlation coefficients of experimental variables, target speech proportion, and feature distortions.

	TSP	FD _p	FD _E	FD _T	FD _L
N	-0.59 ^a	0.18 ^a	0.30 ^a	0.29 ^a	0.49 ^a
Δ	0.06 ^b	0.02	0.03	0.25 ^a	0.47 ^a
α	0.06 ^b	-0.14 ^a	-0.22 ^a	0.45 ^a	0.23 ^a
TSP		0.03	-0.23 ^a	-0.15 ^a	-0.23 ^a

^a $p < 0.001$.

^b $p < 0.05$.

The other correlations were close to zero; their significance values were likely due to the large number of runs.

To estimate the influence of the TSP on model scores, TSP was added as a predictor variable to the initial LRM (see Table I). Table III shows the difference in LRM deviance (where a negative value indicates better model predictions) and the regression coefficients for the added variable. It should be noted that by adding another variable to the LRM, the β -coefficients of the initial variables (Table I) also change. These new β -coefficients are not reported here. The results show that adding the TSP to the LRM significantly improved the prediction of model scores for all tasks. The positive β -coefficient indicates that a higher TSP indeed improved model scores.

3. Feature distortions

The feature distortion values were calculated for each run as described in Sec. IID2. As with the calculation of the TSP, the signal segments used for the calculation correspond to the target word Baron for identification and localization, and to the target color and number words for color and number word recognition. FD values for the different spatial

TABLE III. Differences in deviance compared to the initial model (LRM, Table I) when the variable TSP was added as a single factor (without interactions); the significance levels show whether the model predictions are significantly different from the previous one. The bottom line shows the corresponding β -coefficient of the new variable TSP in the model, including its significance level. It is important to note that all other predictor coefficients change when the new variable is added. These changes are not shown here.

	identification	localization	color word rec.	number word rec.
deviance difference	-20.16 ^a	-33.47 ^a	-8.71 ^b	-13.85 ^a
regression coeff. β	18.89(4.68) ^a	24.81(5.04) ^a	11.77(4.20) ^b	10.56(3.08) ^a

^a $p < 0.001$.

^b $p < 0.01$.

conditions are shown in Fig. 9. Table II shows the partial correlation coefficients for the experimental variables, TSP and FD (last four columns). The periodicity and periodic energy feature distortions were relatively constant in the different conditions, which is also reflected in their relatively low partial correlation coefficients. These distortions tended to increase with an increasing number of talkers, and they tended to decrease with a larger absolute target azimuth. The feature distortions of the interaural time and level differences were significantly larger when the target-to-masker distance Δ and the absolute target azimuth α increased.

To examine the influence of the FDs on model scores, they were added as variables to the previous LRM including the TSP. The difference of model deviation when the new variable was added and the β value of each variable in the new model are shown in Table IV. Interestingly, distortions of periodicity features seem to have had no influence on

FIG. 9. Mean and standard deviations of the feature distortions as a function of target location for the five spatial conditions. Note that feature distortion is expressed in units of σ_p , σ_E , σ_T , and σ_L [see Eqs. (5) to (8)].

TABLE IV. Differences in deviance compared to the initial model (LRM, with the variables in Table I and the TSP) when the feature distortions FD_X are added as single factors (without interactions). The respective bottom lines show the corresponding β value of the new variable in the model. It is important to note that all other predictor coefficients change when the new variable is added. These changes are not shown here.

	identification	localization	color word rec.	number word rec.
FD_P : dev. diff.	-2.22	-2.77	-0.002	-0.69
FD_P : regr. coeff. β	-0.26(0.18)	-0.29(0.17)	0.009(0.192)	-0.15(0.18)
FD_E : dev. diff.	-4.90 ^a	-10.91 ^b	-5.42 ^a	-4.25 ^a
FD_E : regr. coeff. β	-1.98(0.91) ^a	-3.04(0.96) ^c	-1.31	-1.21(0.59) ^a
FD_T : dev. diff.	-1.22	-7.20 ^c	-0.72	-0.07
FD_T : regr. coeff. β	-0.04(0.04)	-0.11(0.04) ^c	0.04(0.05)	0.009(0.033)
FD_L : dev. diff.	-3.94 ^a	-17.84 ^b	-0.23	-0.21
FD_L : regr. coeff. β	-0.56(0.29)	-1.30(0.33) ^b	0.16(0.34)	-0.10(0.23)

^a $p < 0.05$.

^b $p < 0.001$.

^c $p < 0.01$.

model scores. Distortions of periodic energy, however, had a negative influence on model scores, as reflected in their negative β -values. Distortions of interaural time and level differences had a strong influence on localization performance. Although the target identification task depends on the model localization, it is only weakly influenced by distortions of ITD and ILD.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study presents an auditory model that can (1) localize and identify a target talker in a multi-talker mixture and (2) recognize words uttered by the target talker from a limited set of known words. The model word recognition scores were found to be comparable to subject results by [Brungart and Simpson \(2007\)](#) for most conditions. The main purpose of the model was to investigate whether the use of robust information (glimpses) and the classification of these glimpses using a feature-based template matching procedure with clean speech templates is sufficient to account for the ability to localize, identify and understand a target talker in a multi-talker mixture. However, the model relies on specific *a priori* knowledge that is not available to the subjects, in particular, the availability of clean word samples from all talkers at all possible locations, and perfect knowledge about the time position and duration of the words to be recognized. Therefore, the model estimates can be seen as an upper limit of model performance.

A. Comparison of model and subject performance

The model results for word recognition did not differ significantly from the subject results for most of the tested conditions. This finding indicates that the feature glimpses extracted from a multi-talker signal could contain sufficient information for solving word recognition tasks in a complex acoustic scene. The most prominent difference between model and subject results was observed when the target was placed in the right hemifield: in these cases, the subjects performed significantly better than the model. [Brungart and Simpson \(2007\)](#) argued that subjects may have performed better when the target was placed in the right rather than in the left hemifield because the brain areas that process speech

are primarily located in the left hemisphere. The model does not include a mechanism for distinguishing between left and right hemifields, so performance was expected to be the same for both. A statistical analysis using a two-tailed binomial test on the word recognition data indeed revealed no significant differences between “mirrored” locations. Another significant difference is observed in the three-talker-close condition when the target is located at 0° . Here, the model performs significantly better than the subjects. This could be either an effect of using different HRTFs than the subjects, or it might be a result from the fact that the model uses more *a priori* information than is available to the subjects.

[Brungart and Simpson \(2007\)](#) found that subject performance decreased when there were more competing talkers. The same relation was observed in the model’s performance, but only for localization and identification; little or no correlation was found for word recognition when the model had perfect knowledge of target location and identity. Since word recognition performance of the default model depends on localization and identification performance, a similar decrease in word recognition performance was seen in the model data. One possible explanation for the decrease in performance is a lower ratio of target-related time-frequency bins, i.e., the TSP, in the mixture when more talkers were present. This correlation was indeed found in this study and therefore supports the findings of [Cooke \(2006\)](#), for example. It should be noted, however, that [Cooke \(2006\)](#) measured slightly lower glimpse proportions; this is because he limited his definition of a glimpse to connected time-frequency areas with at least four connected bins, whereas the present study used single time-frequency bins, with the same glimpsing threshold of 3 dB in local SNR as used by [Cooke \(2006\)](#). The TSP is a significant factor on the model scores. The higher the TSP, the higher are the model scores in terms of identification, localization, color word, and number word recognition. A similar relationship was also shown by [Cooke \(2006\)](#) for subject consonant recognition performance. Another hypothesis explaining the relation between word recognition performance and number of talkers is that feature distortions are higher for more talkers; higher feature

distortions may lead to inaccuracies in the matching procedure with clean-speech templates. In the present study, the number of talkers was positively correlated with feature distortions. Feature distortions had a relatively large effect on model localization performance, which supports this second hypothesis, at least for this specific task.

The psychoacoustic data show that humans perform better for lateral than for central target positions (Brungart and Simpson, 2007). The model data show a similar trend, but only for localization and identification performance; word recognition performance with perfect *a priori* information on target identity and location did not depend on target position. Thus, the word recognition performance drop for the (default) model is caused by a performance drop in localization and identification. This may also apply to human subjects, because an impaired *a priori* knowledge about the talker location and voice characteristics has been connected to lower word recognition scores (Ericson *et al.*, 2004). However, the most common explanation for a better human performance for lateral than for central positions is that humans make use of the better ear, where the SNR is relatively high (e.g., Brungart and Simpson, 2007). Further psychoacoustic research is needed to disentangle the influence of better ear listening and target uncertainty.

The psychoacoustic study also examined the effects of target-to-masker distance on word recognition performance: performance was better for the “far” conditions than for the “close” conditions. In the model scores, this behavior was only seen in the word recognition task in the two-talker condition with the ideal model (i.e., with perfect information on target identity and location). One hypothesis for this finding might be that in the far condition, the different speech “streams” can be more easily distinguished from each other, because the binaural features differ more strongly. However, this hypothesis was not explicitly examined in this study. Another hypothesis might be that for larger target-to-masker distances, the binaural feature distortions become larger. This was indeed observed in the correlation data. However, for word recognition, the binaural feature distortions did not seem to play a major role. Therefore, the influence of feature distortions remains unclear. Another interesting finding is that for model localization and identification performance, a difference between close and far conditions was observed in the three-talker condition, but performance was *better* for the close condition than for the far condition. This may be because the binaural feature distortions were indeed lower for the close condition and binaural feature distortions played a large role, at least for localization performance, unlike for word recognition.

It is interesting to note that the experimental variables had a potentially large influence on model localization and identification performance, but their influence on word recognition was rather small. That is, the differences in word recognition performance that arose from changes in the experimental variables resulted mainly from the differences in localization and identification performance. To what extent this also applies to human perception needs to be investigated further.

B. Differences in the psychoacoustic and model setups

When comparing the subject and model results it is important to note that the setup and experimental procedures differed in some aspects. First, the talker locations differed in the two-talker-far condition ($\pm 60^\circ$ for the model simulations vs $\pm 90^\circ$ in the psychoacoustic study), in the three-talker-far condition ($[0^\circ, \pm 60^\circ]$ vs $[0^\circ, \pm 90^\circ]$) and in the four-talker condition ($[\pm 20^\circ, \pm 60^\circ]$ vs $[\pm 30^\circ, \pm 90^\circ]$). However, model and subject results are still comparable, because human subject performance presumably does not differ for target azimuths of 90° versus 60° (or, 20° versus 40° in the four-talker condition). This can be concluded from psychoacoustic studies that measured the spatial release from masking (SRM) as a function of the angular target-masker separation: Jones and Litovsky (2011) found that the considerably larger amount of changes in SRM takes place between separations of 0° and 45° , and there is almost no difference observed between 45° and 90° . Hawley *et al.* (1999) found a similar result. Brungart and Simpson (2007) found that there is no significant difference in word scores for competing sentences being placed at $\pm 5^\circ$ or $\pm 90^\circ$. We therefore assume that model and subject results can be compared in spite of the differences in spatial configuration.

The second difference was that Brungart and Simpson (2007) also investigated certain dynamics in the scene. For this purpose, different transition types occurred within a block of trials: (1) the target phrase switched to a different talker and position while all talkers remained at fixed positions, (2) the target phrase moved to another position while the target talker identity remained fixed, (3) the target phrase moved to another position and talker, and all talkers changed their positions randomly from trial to trial. The role of the transition probabilities was also investigated; the probabilities ranged from 0 (no transition within a block of trials) to 1 (transition in every trial). They found that word recognition for transitions of type (1) and (3) were worse than for type (2), and that word recognition performance decreased with increasing transition probability. The simulations in the model resemble transition type (3) with a transition probability of 1; this configuration is one of the most difficult for human listeners. However, the psychoacoustic results that we used here for comparison with the model were accumulated across all transition types and probabilities and are therefore possibly better than the isolated results of transition type (3) and transition probability 1. In addition, the model did not take into account that in one block of trials, the same spatial configuration was always used, which possibly led to a build-up of more accurate *a priori* information about the location of the talkers. Incorporating this knowledge into the model could possibly enhance the results further.

C. Other factors influencing model scores

The analysis of other factors influencing model scores revealed significant influences of talker identity and target word. Darwin *et al.* (2003) also observed performance differences between talker identities for the same speech corpus as used in this study. They found that the intonation patterns of

different call signs, i.e., the F0 contour, differed more or less depending on talker identity. If the variation in the intonation pattern is generally high, this is thought to provide an additional cue for segregating the call sign from other words. Brungart (2001) also found significant differences in word recognition performance for different talker identities in experiments using the same speech corpus. It is not possible to determine how the talker identity labels of the two aforementioned studies correspond to the labels used in this study, so that detailed comparisons cannot be made. However, it is clear from the previous studies that subjects also perform differently for different target talkers, a behavior that is also reflected in the model results presented here. Additionally, it should be noted that the influence of talker identity and the number of competing talkers could not be completely disentangled: for example, the talker with the identity “D” had a negative impact on model scores, but it is not clear whether this was because this talker was generally more difficult to understand, or because this talker only appeared in the four-talker condition, where performance was already worse than for the two- and three-talker conditions.

Brungart (2001) also investigated the influence of the target word on subject word recognition performance. He found that the color word white and the number word five could be recognized better than the other words. Similar results were found in the model data in this study, where the color word white and the number word five yielded 100% recognition scores.

D. Comparison to other multi-talker scene models

The model task of localizing a target talker in a multi-talker mixture, presented in this study, is similar to the task described by Josupeit *et al.* (2016). The present model takes up the main concepts of that study and extends and modifies these concepts towards a more unified model that is able to do other tasks, not only localization. Josupeit *et al.* (2016) used a template matching approach which is also applied in the present study. However, due to the differences in the experimental setup, the templates were calculated differently: In the previous study, there was one constant target utterance used throughout the whole experiment; in the present study, there could be multiple realizations of the target word Baron as well as up to four different target talkers. Therefore, in the present study, target templates were PDFs, rather than distinct target features, as in the previous study. The usage of PDFs as templates prepares the way for setups with less *a priori* information about the target. In those setups, distinct word templates cannot be used any more, but PDFs could be calculated from expectations about the target state, e.g., based on previous observations. Another modification of the present model is the probabilistic approach. In the previous model, a “0 or 1” decision was made for each time-frequency bin, indicating whether it was dominated by the target or not. Here, instead, we followed a probabilistic classification throughout the whole model process, and the final decision was then based on the highest probability. This procedure therefore applies neuroscientific knowledge about the “probabilistic brain” (Pouget *et al.*, 2013).

Another similar model available in the literature is a speech recognition model by Srinivasan and Wang (2008) that is applied to multi-talker scenes consisting of CRM sentences. Their approach was to estimate a binary mask of the scene which was used to eliminate masker-related time-frequency bins from the signal and use the remaining bins for a missing-data automatic speech recognition (ASR) system. Only monaural signals were used so that it is difficult to compare their model’s performance to the performance of the model in the present study. However, it is interesting to explore the similarities and differences between the two models. To calculate the binary masks, Srinivasan and Wang (2008) used *a priori* knowledge about the pitch tracks of the target and interferers. In the model presented here, only the feature tracks of the target were used. In contrast to the model by Srinivasan and Wang (2008), we used not only periodicity, but also periodic energy and binaural features. Another difference is that Srinivasan and Wang (2008) applied a pitch-based segregation based on segmentation and grouping (Hu and Wang, 2004) that involves a cross channel correlation as well as temporal continuity. In our model, no cross-channel processes are applied and each channel is initially analysed independently of the others. A temporal continuity is implicitly applied when using the time contours of features as templates. The other major difference between the two models is the classification process. Srinivasan and Wang (2008) used a missing-data ASR classifier based on Hidden Markov Models whereas our classification process is an hypothesis-based approach using template matching. The performance of the model by Srinivasan and Wang (2008) for almost unmanipulated input signals (only time-frequency bins below an SNR of -60 dB were cut from the signal), and two talkers of the same sex is about 55% word recognition performance, compared to around 72% word recognition measured in human subjects for the same setup (Chang, 2004). The model presented here shows a better match with the subject results for the two-talker close condition, i.e., an approximately 80% mean model score compared to an approximately 90.5% mean subject score. However, we cannot predict how our model would behave for monaural signal presentations.

E. Model limitations, implications, and further development

The model is based on several assumptions that utilize prior information in an optimal way. One of these assumptions is that internal representations exist in the form of clean feature-based templates, and that these templates exist for each of the hypotheses to be tested. This assumption could be made, because there is some evidence that the auditory system is able to build up robust memory from repeated auditory input (Agus *et al.*, 2010). This memory could be built up in the training phase and utilized in the testing phase of the experiment.

Another point worth mentioning is that the model uses *a priori* knowledge about the time position and duration of the target words. In further model developments, this issue could

be handled with onset/offset detectors, or by applying systematic time shifts to the template matching procedure.

The experimental setup had the special characteristic that the talker identities, the possible locations, and the possible words were limited. Hence, it was possible to apply a template-based classification scheme. For more realistic scenarios with unknown talker identities and an unlimited set of possible words, this template-based classification could not be applied any more. In these cases, the templates might be replaced by expectations about the feature tracks, e.g., based on what was observed in previous time frames. This procedure could be, for example, implemented as sequential Monte Carlo methods (Nix and Hohmann, 2007) or hidden Markov models (Mysore and Smaragdis, 2011).

The main purpose of the study was to test the hypothesis that the sparse glimpsed periodicity-based spectral and interaural features provide sufficient information to decode speech information from a complex multi-talker condition when using prior information from a clean speech reference only. We feel it is a major contribution of this study to implement the approach, critically test it, and to find support for the hypothesis in the data. This approach contributes to the body of findings on possible ASA schemes in humans and machines in that it paves the way towards dramatically reducing the combinatoric effort required to decode such complex scenes. The template-based classification approach exploits the information conveyed by the glimpses in an optimal way. Results therefore constitute the upper margin of performance. Future work will include less salient consonant-based information, e.g., from onset features, and will investigate more realistic speech-model based classification schemes [e.g., sequential Monte Carlo methods (Nix and Hohmann, 2007), or novelty-based processing methods (Schwartenbeck *et al.*, 2013)].

V. CONCLUSIONS

- (1) Periodicity-based salient features provide a sparse auditory time-frequency representation and contain sufficient information to decode complex auditory scenes. The classification scheme introduced in this model allows a relatively easy integration of additional features, e.g., consonant-related features.
- (2) The sole focus on salient features allows the usage of clean speech models for classification. Thus, computational complexity that arises from using sound source superposition models may be greatly reduced in models of computational auditory scene analysis.
- (3) The suggested model can successfully detect the relevant target-dominated time-frequency bins and may therefore be used as a preprocessor to ASR systems. This could be done by exploiting the support value in each time-frequency bin that is evoked by the template with the highest overall support. The support in each time-frequency bin could then be used to generate a gray mask or—by selecting a suitable support threshold—a binary mask for a missing data ASR system.
- (4) By restricting the model to salient periodicity-related features, spectro-temporal “landmarks” with high

information content are identified. These landmarks may form the first stage of hierarchical scene analysis models, which process less robust features, such as onset and offset or consonant-related spectro-temporal features, in a subsequent step.

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APPENDIX A: SYNCHROGRAM CALCULATION AND FEATURE EXTRACTION

In this appendix, a mathematical description of the feature extraction stage is given. In the following, the output signal of the preprocessing stage is termed $x_{cs}(k)$; the sampling frequency of this signal is $f_s = 40$ kHz. All subsequent auditory features are extracted every 10 ms, i.e., with a sampling frequency of $f_1 = 100$ Hz. Therefore, two types of time indices are used in the following: Indices k and l refer to time signals with a sampling frequency of $f_s = 40$ kHz; the index n refers to auditory features that vary across time with a sampling frequency of $f_1 = 100$ Hz.

The normalized synchrogram (Chen and Hohmann, 2015) is defined as follows:

$$\text{synch}_{\text{cns}}(P') = \frac{E_{P;\text{cns}}(P')}{E_{\text{tot};\text{cns}}(P')}. \quad (\text{A1})$$

$E_{P;\text{cns}}(P')$ is the periodic energy for the period length P' , given in seconds; $E_{\text{tot};\text{cns}}(P')$ is the corresponding total energy. A more detailed description of the energy calculations is given in the following.

The output time signal of the auditory preprocessing stage is given by $x_{cs}(k)$. To determine the periodic energy, first, the mean signal v of 8 signal segments of length $N_{P'} = f_s P'$ around the time n is calculated,

$$v_{\text{cns},P'}(l) = \frac{1}{8} \sum_{j=-4}^3 x_{cs}(k(n) + l + jN_{P'}), \quad (\text{A2})$$

where $k(n)$ is a time index of the original signal; it can be converted to the index n via the formula $k(n) = (n-1)(f_s/f_1) + 1$ or $n(k) = (k-1)(f_1/f_s) + 1$. $v_{\text{cns},P'}(l)$ is termed the base function for a period P' . As the time index l is given in samples, l ranges from 1 to $N_{P'}$. The periodic energy for a period length P' is then given by the mean square value of the elements in v ,

$$E_{P;\text{cns}}(P') = \frac{1}{N_{P'}} \sum_{l=1}^{N_{P'}} (v_{\text{cns},P'}(l))^2. \quad (\text{A3})$$

E_P has high values whenever P' resembles the actual signal period. Values of P' different from the actual period lead to cancellation due to the computation of the mean in Eq. (A2), and thus to a decrease in the energy of v .

The total energy is given by the mean square value of the original signal $x_{cs}(k)$, covering the same range as all eight signal segments,

$$E_{\text{tot},cns}(P') = \frac{1}{8N_{P'}} \sum_{l=1}^{8N_{P'}} (x_{cs}(k(n) + l - 4N_{P'}))^2. \quad (\text{A4})$$

The periodicity feature extraction is based on the normalized synchrogram $\text{synch}_{cns}(P')$. The aim was to extract only those period values corresponding to a high periodic energy. First of all, all local maxima are extracted from the normalized synchrogram, forming the set $P_{\text{peak},cns}$,

$$P_{\text{peak},cns} = \{P' \in P_{\text{range}} \mid \text{synch}_{cns}(P') \text{ is a local maximum}\}. \quad (\text{A5})$$

A local maximum is defined as a value whose two neighboring values are both lower. P_{range} is the set of possible periodicity values,

$$P_{\text{range}} = \{P_{\min}, P_{\min} + \Delta P, \dots, P_{\max} - \Delta P, P_{\max}\}, \quad (\text{A6})$$

with $P_{\min} = (1400 \text{ Hz})^{-1}$ and $P_{\max} = (80 \text{ Hz})^{-1}$; ΔP corresponds to one sample at f_s . The corresponding set of synchrogram peak values is given by

$$\text{synch}_{\text{peak},cns} = \{\text{synch}_{cns}(P') \mid P' \in P_{\text{peak},cns}\}. \quad (\text{A7})$$

The final periodicity features are the peak locations with relatively high peak values; that is, only those periodicities are selected as glimpses whose periodic energy is high enough. The first criterion that must be fulfilled is a high enough harmonic content,

$$P_{\text{cand},cns} = \begin{cases} P_{\text{peak},cns} & \text{if } \max(\text{synch}_{\text{peak},cns}) > P_1, \\ \emptyset & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A8})$$

P_1 was set to 0.9 for the fine structure filters channels and to 0.5 for the envelope channels (Josupeit *et al.*, 2016). The second criterion is to select all periodicity values that exceed a threshold of P_2 in the normalized synchrogram. Thus, all selected periodicity glimpses are given by

$$P_{cns} = \{P' \in P_{\text{cand},cns} \mid \text{synch}_{cns}(P') > P_2\}. \quad (\text{A9})$$

P_2 was set to 0.8 for the fine structure filters channels and to 0.4 for the envelope channels (Josupeit *et al.*, 2016). The periodic energy features are given by

$$E_{cns} = \{E_{P;cns}(P') \mid P' \in P_{cns}\}. \quad (\text{A10})$$

The extraction of interaural level differences (ILDs) and interaural time differences (ITDs) is based on the left and right channel base functions, $v_{cn1,P'}(l)$ and $v_{cn2,P'}(l)$, as defined in Eq. (A2). For the calculation of the ILDs, the periodic energies of these base functions are extracted as in Eq. (A3). The ILD glimpses are then calculated as

$$L_{cns} = \left\{ 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{E_{P;cns2}(P')}{E_{P;cns1}(P')} \right) \mid P' \in P_{cns} \right\}. \quad (\text{A11})$$

The extraction of ITDs is based on the cross-correlation function of $v_{cn1,P'}(l)$ and $v_{cn2,P'}(l)$. In the following, this cross-correlation function is termed $X_{c,n,P';-P':P'}$. Essentially, the maximum location of X is then defined as the ITD. Because ambiguities between left and right ITDs are possible, a case differentiation based on the extracted ILDs is applied, so that the extracted ITDs are defined as

$$T_{cns} = \begin{cases} \left\{ \text{argmax}(X_{c,n,P';-P':0}) \mid P' \in P_{cns} \right\} & \text{if } L_{cns} < -1 \text{ dB}, \\ \left\{ \text{argmax}(X_{c,n,P';0:P'}) \mid P' \in P_{cns} \right\} & \text{if } L_{cns} > +1 \text{ dB}, \\ \left\{ \text{argmax}(X_{c,n,P';-P':P'}) \mid P' \in P_{cns} \right\} & \text{if } |L_{cns}| < 1 \text{ dB}. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A12})$$

It should be noted here that the ILD and ITD glimpse sets L_{cns} and T_{cns} may contain different values for the two sides s , because the set of selected periodicities P_{cns} may differ between the two sides.

APPENDIX B: TEMPLATE GENERATION

This appendix covers a mathematical description of the template generation. To calculate the templates, first, the glimpses are extracted from each existent utterance of the clean word w in the corpus, spoken by talker i from direction α . For the call sign (Baron) and each of the number words, there were $K_w = 32$ utterances per talker; for each of the color words, there were $K_w = 64$ utterances per talker. The feature extraction procedure is the same as in Sec. II C 1; in the following, the extracted glimpses for utterance m of a word w are termed $P'_{cns}(w, i, \alpha, m)$, $E'_{cns}(w, i, \alpha, m)$, $T'_{cns}(w, i, \alpha, m)$, and $L'_{cns}(w, i, \alpha, m)$. The index t denotes ‘‘template-related’’ features. The feature sets for all utterances m are then combined into a multiset

$$P'_{cns}(w, i, \alpha) = \biguplus_{m=1}^{K_w} P'_{cns}(w, i, \alpha, m), \quad (\text{B1})$$

and analogously for the other features. A multiset is the same as a set, but with the difference that it can contain multiple elements of the same value. A multiset sum, written as \biguplus , is the mathematical union of different (multi)sets to a multiset. The templates are then generated as the sum across Gaussian kernels of all elements of the multiset $P'_{cns}(w, i, \alpha)$,

$$\text{PDF}_{cns}(P|w, i, \alpha) = C_0 \sum_{P' \in P'_{cns}(w, i, \alpha)} \mathcal{N}(P', \sigma_P), \quad (\text{B2})$$

where $f(P) = \mathcal{N}(\mu, \sigma)$ denotes a Gaussian kernel, i.e., a normal distribution with expected value μ and standard deviation σ ; C_0 is a normalization constant chosen so that $\text{PDF}_{cns}(P|w, i, \alpha)$ is a probability density function with respect to the variable P . The same procedure is applied to calculate the other feature templates, denoted as $\text{PDF}_{cns}(E|w, i, \alpha)$, $\text{PDF}_{cns}(T|w, i, \alpha)$, and $\text{PDF}_{cns}(L|w, i, \alpha)$. The width σ of the Gaussian kernels was chosen so that it corresponds to the just noticeable differences (JNDs) of the respective features, as defined in Eqs. (5) to (8).

¹In those studies, the term “glimpses” was used to denote time-frequency bins that are dominated by the talker of interest; note that this definition is different from the one used in this paper, where a glimpse can be either target or masker.

²The integral calculated using the trapezoid rule is defined as

$$I(f(x), \Delta x) = \frac{\Delta x}{2} (f(x - \Delta x) + f(x)) + \frac{\Delta x}{2} (f(x) + f(x + \Delta x)),$$

where $f(x)$ is a function, and Δx is the difference between values at which the function is evaluated.

³The logistic regression model with two possible outcomes (here, 1 for correct response or 0 for incorrect response) estimates the best fitting coefficients β_i for the formula

$$\text{logit}(P(Y_i = 1)) = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^{M_1} \beta_j X_{ji} + \sum_{k=M_1+1}^{M_2} \beta_k \times (\text{interactions}).$$

M_1 is the number of variables used for model prediction; interaction terms are defined as the product of different variables ($X_{j_1 i} X_{j_2 i}$); M_2 is the total number of coefficients estimated, including coefficients for interaction terms.

- Agus, T. R., Thorpe, S. J., and Pressnitzer, D. (2010). “Rapid formation of robust auditory memories: Insights from noise,” *Neuron* **66**(4), 610–618.
- Assmann, P. F., and Summerfield, Q. (1989). “Modeling the perception of concurrent vowels: Vowels with the same fundamental frequency,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **85**(1), 327–338.
- Best, V., Mason, C. R., Swaminathan, J., Kidd, G., Jr., Jakien, K. M., Kämpel, S. D., Gallun, F. J., Buchholz, J. M., and Glyde, H. (2016). “On the contribution of target audibility to performance in spatialized speech mixtures,” in *Physiology, Psychoacoustics and Cognition in Normal and Impaired Hearing* (Springer, Berlin), pp. 83–91.
- Bolia, R. S., Nelson, W. T., Ericson, M. A., and Simpson, B. D. (2000). “A speech corpus for multi-talker communications research,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **107**(2), 1065–1066.
- Brungart, D. S. (2001). “Informational and energetic masking effects in the perception of two simultaneous talkers,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **109**(3), 1101–1109.
- Brungart, D. S., and Rabinowitz, W. M. (1999). “Auditory localization of nearby sources. Head-related transfer functions,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **106**(3), 1465–1479.
- Brungart, D. S., and Simpson, B. D. (2007). “Cocktail party listening in a dynamic multi-talker environment,” *Percept. Psychophys.* **69**(1), 79–91.
- Chang, P. S. (2004). “Exploration of behavioral, physiological, and computational approaches to auditory scene analysis,” Department of Computer and Information Science, Ohio State University, Columbus, 131 pp.
- Chen, Z., and Hohmann, V. (2015). “Online monaural speech enhancement based on periodicity analysis and *a priori* SNR estimation,” *IEEE/ACM Trans. Audio Speech Lang. Process.* **23**(11), 1904–1916.
- Cherry, E. C. (1953). “Some experiments on the recognition of speech, with one and with two ears,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **25**(5), 975–979.
- Cooke, M. (2006). “A glimpsing model of speech perception in noise,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **119**(3), 1562–1573.
- Culling, J. F., and Darwin, C. J. (1994). “Perceptual and computational separation of simultaneous vowels: Cues arising from low-frequency beating,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **95**(3), 1559–1569.
- Culling, J. F., Hawley, M. L., and Litovsky, R. Y. (2004). “The role of head-induced interaural time and level differences in the speech reception threshold for multiple interfering sound sources,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **116**(2), 1057–1065.
- Darwin, C. J. (2008). “Listening to speech in the presence of other sounds,” *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. London B: Biol. Sci.* **363**(1493), 1011–1021.
- Darwin, C. J., Brungart, D. S., and Simpson, B. D. (2003). “Effects of fundamental frequency and vocal-tract length changes on attention to one of two simultaneous talkers,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **114**(5), 2913–2922.
- Darwin, C. J., and Hukin, R. W. (1999). “Auditory objects of attention: The role of interaural time differences,” *J. Exp. Psychol.: Human Percept. Perform.* **25**(3), 617–629.
- Dietz, M., Ewert, S. D., and Hohmann, V. (2011). “Auditory model based direction estimation of concurrent speakers from binaural signals,” *Speech Commun.* **53**(5), 592–605.
- Drennan, W. R., Gatehouse, S., and Lever, C. (2003). “Perceptual segregation of competing speech sounds: The role of spatial location,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **114**(4), 2178–2189.
- Du, Y., He, Y., Ross, B., Bardouille, T., Wu, X., Li, L., and Alain, C. (2011). “Human auditory cortex activity shows additive effects of spectral and spatial cues during speech segregation,” *Cerebral Cortex* **21**(3), 698–707.
- Ellis, D. P. (1999). “Using knowledge to organize sound: The prediction-driven approach to computational auditory scene analysis and its application to speech/nonspeech mixtures,” *Speech Commun.* **27**(3), 281–298.
- Ericson, M. A., Brungart, D. S., and Simpson, B. D. (2004). “Factors that influence intelligibility in multitalker speech displays,” *Int. J. Aviation Psychol.* **14**(3), 313–334.
- Faller, C., and Merimaa, J. (2004). “Source localization in complex listening situations: Selection of binaural cues based on interaural coherence,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **116**(5), 3075–3089.
- Gregory, R. L. (1997). “Knowledge in perception and illusion,” *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. London B: Biol. Sci.* **352**(1358), 1121–1127.
- Hawley, M. L., Litovsky, R. Y., and Colburn, H. S. (1999). “Speech intelligibility and localization in a multi-source environment,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **105**(6), 3436–3448.
- Hu, G., and Wang, D. (2004). “Monaural speech segregation based on pitch tracking and amplitude modulation,” *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw.* **15**(5), 1135–1150.
- Jones, G. L., and Litovsky, R. Y. (2011). “A cocktail party model of spatial release from masking by both noise and speech interferers,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **130**(3), 1463–1474.
- Josupeit, A., Kopčo, N., and Hohmann, V. (2016). “Modeling of speech localization in a multi-talker mixture using periodicity and energy-based auditory features,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **139**(5), 2911–2923.
- Kayser, H., Ewert, S. D., Anemüller, J., Rohdenburg, T., Hohmann, V., and Kollmeier, B. (2009). “Database of multichannel in-ear and behind-the-ear head-related and binaural room impulse responses,” *EURASIP J. Adv. Sign. Process.* **2009**, 6.
- Moore, B. C., and Gockel, H. E. (2012). “Properties of auditory stream formation,” *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. B* **367**(1591), 919–931.
- Mysore, G. J., and Smaragdīs, P. (2011, May). “A non-negative approach to semi-supervised separation of speech from noise with the use of temporal dynamics,” in *2011 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)* (IEEE), pp. 17–20.
- Nix, J., and Hohmann, V. (2007). “Combined estimation of spectral envelopes and sound source direction of concurrent voices by multidimensional statistical filtering,” *IEEE Trans. Audio Speech Lang. Process.* **15**(3), 995–1008.
- Pouget, A., Beck, J. M., Ma, W. J., and Latham, P. E. (2013). “Probabilistic brains: Knowns and unknowns,” *Nat. Neurosci.* **16**(9), 1170–1178.
- Schoenmaker, E., and van de Par, S. (2016). “Intelligibility for binaural speech with discarded low-SNR speech components,” in *Physiology, Psychoacoustics and Cognition in Normal and Impaired Hearing* (Springer, Berlin), pp. 73–81.
- Schwartenbeck, P., FitzGerald, T., Dolan, R., and Friston, K. (2013). “Exploration, novelty, surprise, and free energy minimization,” *Front. Psychol.* **4**, 710.
- Srinivasan, S., and Wang, D. (2008). “A model for multitalker speech perception,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **124**(5), 3213–3224.
- Summers, R. J., Bailey, P. J., and Roberts, B. (2010). “Effects of differences in fundamental frequency on across-formant grouping in speech perception,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **128**(6), 3667–3677.
- Yost, W. A. (1974). “Discriminations of interaural phase differences,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **55**(6), 1299–1303.
- Yost, W. A., and Dye, R. H., Jr., (1988). “Discrimination of interaural differences of level as a function of frequency,” *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **83**(5), 1846–1851.
- Zwicker, E., and Fastl, H. (2007). *Psychoacoustics: Facts and Models*, 2nd ed. (Springer Science & Business Media, New York), Vol. 22, 417 pp.